

Supplementary materials:

Nanoscale soft wetting observed in Co/Sapphire during pulsed laser irradiation

Jung Won Choi¹, Daseul Ham², Seonghyun Han¹, Do Young Noh^{1,*}, Hyon Chol Kang^{2,*}

¹School of Materials Science and Engineering, Department of Physics and Photon Science, Gwangju Institute of Science and Technology, Gwangju, 61005, Korea

²Department of Materials Science and Engineering, Chosun University, Gwangju 61452, Korea

*E-mail: dynoh@gist.ac.kr, kanghc@chosun.ac.kr

Figure S1. (a) Low-magnification scanning TEM image and (b) EDX mapping image of a Co NP. Wetting ridges are clearly observed at the contact line.

Figure S2. TEM and EDX mapping images highlighting the left corner of the wetting ridge near the contact line. (a) Scanning TEM image. EDX mapping images of (b) Co_K, (c) O_K, (d) Al_K emissions. The color map in (e) clearly shows the wetting ridge.